

Clustering COVID-19 mortality time series

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Abstract. The undisputed assumption during the COVID-19 pandemic, was that the isolated pathogen SARS-COV-2 was spreading worldwide with the same mortal effects. However, examining the mortality records it is possible to appreciate substantial differences between countries in their response to the pandemic. This paper looks for clusters of countries that may share some features explaining the diversity of the response. First, the paper extracts latent mortality patterns by Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Independent Component Analysis (ICA), and Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NNMF). Clustering is then carried out over the coefficients of the respective transformations of the countries mortality time series. The choice of the number of latent patterns has been guided by the explained variance in PCA and the avoidance of overfitting taking into account the ratio of representatives to the size of the dataset. Additionally, direct clustering of the mortality time series has been carried out by K means. This paper discusses some common findings that point to cultural and socio-economic factors underlying the response.

1 Introduction

Out of the hundreds of thousands of papers published somehow related with COVID-19 pandemic, those dealing with Machine Learning and like predictive approaches were mostly dealing with predicting the individual patient risks for severe disease [5]. Most epidemiological works, have focused on the prediction of the number cases applying epidemiological models [6], classical statistical tools as well as Machine Learning and Deep Learning tools [7].

This paper focus on the retrospective study of mortality time series per country as they provide a more definitive account of the evolution of the pandemic. Coding a decease as COVID-19 has a single confusor which is if the death was due to COVID-19 or it has been incidentally diagnosed but it was not the main cause of death [3]. Nevertheless, the differences in coding criteria may influence the final death toll attributed to the pandemic. In this regard, some studies do consider that many countries in Africa and Asia did not counted properly the death, so they extrapolate a regression model predicting a much higher number of deaths in those countries [8], in this light the catastrophic results in USA do not stand out below the performance of poor countries. Contrary to this view, we take the reported deaths at face value and we try to find clusters of mortality patterns in time that can be associated with underlying conditions in the management of the pandemic response.

To this end, we apply Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Independent Component Analysis (ICA), Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NNMF) in order to find latent components of the mortality time series per country that provide a basis for a reduced dimensionality representation of the time series, which may even be considered as some kind of “explanation”, and it is often used in Machine Learning for feature extraction prior to classification. We carry out clustering of the countries over the features provided by PCA, ICA, and NNMF. Moreover, we carry out the clustering on the raw data by means of K-Means Clustering (KMC) keeping the cluster representatives as templates of mortality time series.

The underlying hypothesis of the pandemic response is that there is a single well isolated and identified pathogen as the cause and that there is only one feasible strategy to cope with it, namely vaccination and social control measures. In other words, because the pathogen is unique the treatment should be the same for everybody and the expected mortality results should be uniform. However, the clustering study reported in this paper shows that mortality results can be very dissimilar between clusters. Such dissimilarity can not be attributed to the pathogen, thus it should be attributed to other conditions, such as geographical localization, enforced policies, and the general health status of the country’s population. Detailed analysis of such conditions is beyond the scope of the paper.

2 Materials and Methods

The code and data are published in zenodo¹ as well as figures and future versions of this work as long as it is evolving.

2.1 Our world in data

“Our world in data” (OWID) is a web site devoted to the publication of relevant data for the pressing geopolitical and economic questions. It is hosted by the University of Oxford and has been extensively funded by Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, thus it is not suspicious of being on the side of the conspiracy theorists. OWID has been publishing relevant data for the follow up of COVID-19 pandemic², aggregating it from several sources. We have used “new_deaths_smoothed_per_million” data for all analysis. Mortality time series were taken from the John Hopkins University COVID-19 site (also extensively funded by Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation) until march 2023, when it stopped updating data after the WHO published the end of the pandemic and most countries stopped reporting. For this work, we have taken the dataset as published on the first days of 2023, which we think covers the pandemic evolution. We consider the seven day rolling average time series, to avoid artifacts due to reporting irregularities, such as zero deaths in weekends.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10403170>

² <https://ourworldindata.org/explorers/coronavirus-data-explorer>

2.2 Mathematical methods

PCA Principal Component Analysis (PCA)[1] is a widely used statistical method in data analysis and dimensionality reduction. In the context of a scientific paper, PCA is often employed to extract essential features or patterns from complex datasets, facilitating a more concise representation of the information contained within the data. The primary objective of PCA is to transform the original variables of a dataset into a new set of uncorrelated variables, called principal components. These components are linear combinations of the original variables and are ordered by the amount of variance they capture. The first principal component accounts for the maximum variance in the data, followed by subsequent components in decreasing order of variance. PCA involves finding the eigenvectors and eigenvalues of the covariance matrix

$$C = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{k=1}^n (X_k - \bar{X})(X_k - \bar{X}).$$

The eigenvectors represent the directions of maximum variance in the data, and the corresponding eigenvalues indicate the magnitude of variance along these directions. The eigenvalue equation is given by $Cv = \lambda v$ where C is the covariance matrix, v is an eigenvector, and λ is the corresponding eigenvalue that corresponds to the variance explained by this eigenvector. The eigenvectors are sorted based on their corresponding eigenvalues in descending order. The eigenvector with the highest eigenvalue corresponds to the first principal component, the second-highest to the second principal component, and so on. The resulting principal components provide a new basis for representing the data, emphasizing the directions of maximum variance and allowing for dimensionality reduction while retaining essential information.

ICA Independent Component Analysis (ICA) [2] is a powerful statistical technique used for blind source separation and the extraction of independent signals from observed mixtures. In the context of this study, ICA was employed to untangle complex relationships within the dataset, revealing hidden patterns and uncovering independent sources of variability. ICA assumes a linear mixing model, where the observed data X is a linear combination of independent source signals S through a mixing matrix A : i.e. $X = A.S$. The goal of ICA is to estimate the inverse of the mixing matrix (A^{-1}) or its pseudoinverse (A^+) to recover the independent source signals (S) from the observed data (X): $S = A^{-1}.X$. ICA relies on statistical measures of independence to guide the estimation of the mixing matrix. Common measures include negentropy, mutual information, and higher-order statistics. One popular algorithm for implementing ICA is FastICA. It is an iterative optimization algorithm that maximizes non-Gaussianity, a surrogate measure for independence. The algorithm iteratively refines estimates of the independent components until convergence.

NNMF Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF)[3] is a mathematical technique used for decomposing a non-negative matrix V of size $m \times n$ into the product of two lower-dimensional matrices, both non-negative, W and H such that $V \approx WH$. NMF minimizes the reconstruction error between the original matrix V and the approximated matrix WH . The objective function often used is the Frobenius norm: $\min_{W,H} \|V - WH\|_F^2$. The optimization process involves iteratively updating W and H to minimize the objective function. Multiplicative Update Rules are commonly used for iterative updates, given by:

$$W_{ij} \leftarrow \frac{(VH^T)_{ij}}{(WHH^T)_{ij}} \quad \text{and} \quad H_{ij} \leftarrow \frac{(W^T V)_{ij}}{(W^T WH)_{ij}}.$$

This method is particularly useful for data analysis, feature extraction, and topic modeling, where the non-negativity constraint ensures the interpretability of the factors. Matrix W represents the basis vectors or features, and matrix H represents the coefficients for combining these features to reconstruct the original data.

K-Means Clustering K-means clustering [4] is a classical unsupervised machine learning algorithm employed for data analysis and pattern recognition. The algorithm operates by partitioning a dataset into K distinct clusters, where each cluster represents a group of data points that share similar characteristics. The process involves iteratively assigning data points to clusters based on proximity and updating cluster centroids until convergence.

2.3 Spectral Clustering

Spectral clustering [11] is a machine learning technique used for partitioning a dataset into meaningful and homogeneous clusters. It is particularly effective when dealing with datasets that exhibit complex structures, such as non-convex shapes or irregular patterns. The process starts with the construction of the similarity graph among the data samples. Then, second eigenvector of the Laplacian of the graph provides the optimal graph cut. In its original formulation, spectral clustering finds the partition of the similarity graph into two clusters, multi-cluster induction is done by recursive splitting of the graph. In this paper, spectral clustering is used on coefficients of PCA, ICA and NNMF to cluster countries into different latent topics which is yielded by each analysis. K-means is not clustered again with spectral clustering.

3 Results

Figure 1 plots the latent components of countries COVID-19 mortality time series induced by PCA, ICA, and NNMF and the cluster representatives found by K-means clustering from the data downloaded from OWID site. The number of latent components was first selected in the PCA approach accounting for 90% of the total variance. Moreover, the ratio of the number of latent components

Fig. 1. The latent representatives of COVID-19 mortality time series uncovered by PCA, ICA, NNMF and K-Means.

Fig. 2. Clustering of countries achieved by K-means into 10 clusters

Fig. 3. Clustering of countries achieved by spectral clustering over the coefficients of PCA transformation considering 10 first eigenvectors and 10 clusters.

Fig. 4. Clustering of countries achieved by spectral clustering over the coefficients of ICA transformation considering 10 components and 10 clusters.

Fig. 5. Clustering of countries achieved by spectral clustering over the coefficients of NNMF transformation considering 10 components and 10 clusters.

to the sample greater than 1:20 seem to be conducting to overfitting. Then, the same number was applied to the other approaches for comparison.

Figures 2, 3, 4, and 5 provide the graphical representation of the country clusters found by K-means, and the spectral clustering over the PCA, ICA, and NNMF respectively. The color coding of the clusters is not preserved between figures, therefore only qualitative appreciations can be extracted from the visualizations.

4 Discussion

Regarding the templates of time series that are shown in Figure 1, only the NNMF patterns give the impression of realistic time series showing features, like the strong peak in spring 2020 that was characteristic of some countries, that can be found in the actual COVID-19 mortality time series. The K-means representatives are, by definition, averages of the mortality patterns of countries in the cluster, therefore representative features are blurred by this averaging process. Regarding PCA and ICA, the latent mortality templates minimize some cost function like the reconstruction error or the statistical independence of latent templates, thus their likelihood as actual templates is not good. For instances, some templates include negative values that are impossible (with the exception of some lousy reporting countries, like Spain). These observations may have some relevance when commenting on the clustering results.

A salient observation is that some western Europe countries (Spain, France, Belgium, Germany, United Kingdom) appear in the same cluster with USA in all approaches, suggesting a strong underlying similarity in pandemic management, and mortality results. Portugal and Italy join this cluster of countries in the K-means and ICA approaches. It is almost self-evident that these countries did apply very similar policies and that their demographics are similar. For instance, they have a very aged population. Older people were the most at risk by this pathogen.

The K-means clustering in Figure 2 is heavily influenced by the magnitude of the data samples. This may explain a large cluster (red color) of countries whose main commonality is that the impact of the pandemic was low relative to population size. Another significant cluster is the USA plus the western Europe countries, Portugal included, which suffered an extraordinary death toll. Another cluster of importance includes Mexico and most areas of South America, with the notable exclusion of Argentina. Argentina and South Africa are clustered in the remaining approaches, maybe due to geographical similarities.

The PCA based clustering in Figure 3 seems to be influenced by the latitude of the countries, so Canada is included in the USA cluster, which also surprisingly includes Peru. However, Australia and New Zealand cluster with Japan, Norway, Finland, and Iceland. There are big clusters of central Africa countries and China, South America countries, and Russia with its neighbors. Notably, Portugal, Italy, Netherlands, Switzerland, Austria and some Balcan states form another cluster. On the other hand, neighboring India and Pakistan do not be-

long to the same cluster. Pakistan join some muslim countries, though it is rather unclear the role of religion in the pandemic response.

The ICA based clustering in Figure 4 is quite similar to the PCA based, if we account for some changes in color assigned to the clusters. Here Portugal, Italy and Netherlands join the USA cluster. The interesting particularity of Portugal is that its response appears out of sync with other European countries, notably with its neighbor Spain in the spring of 2020.

Finally, the NNMF clustering in Figure 5 confirms the USA plus western Europe cluster with the exclusion of Portugal, Ireland, Netherlands and Switzerland, whose patterns are out of sync at some periods of the pandemic, and the inclusion of Peru. On the other hand, Canada and Mexico, which are neighbors of USA form another cluster with Portugal, Ireland, Switzerland, Austria, Netherlands, Israel and Turkey. Other clusters also confirmed with some changes which can be due to the specifics of the NNMF transformation and the aspect of its representatives.

5 Conclusions

We have carried out a clustering of COVID-19 mortality time series per country that finds well defined clusters showing geographical localization as well as some intra-cluster common patterns of response to the pandemic. It is apparent that such well defined differences in pandemic mortality results can not be attributed to the pathogen, which has been declared to be uniformly identified across the globe, thus they must be attributed to pandemic management policies and other conditions. Overall, our results pose more questions than answers are provided. Future works may carry out a more extensive clustering analysis to assess whether the reported clusters are due to computational chance. Also, detailed causal analysis relative to other variables can be carried out in order to find the most dominant pandemic management features that could be related to the diversity of pandemic mortality results.

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